

Think and Prepare: Grit

I want to set long-term goals and have the perseverance to achieve them. I also liked to learn that grit is a strength aside from intelligence and talent. I think there are so many intelligent and talented people capable of achieving many goals, but they lack determination and passion for succeeding. As a result, these people get stuck or conformist to something less than their real potential.

I think a gritty person from the scriptures was Ruth because even though she was having a difficult time when her husband died, she chose to be perseverant and adapt to the changes she was having in her life. Also, she could carry on to the end and never separated from the only person she had left, her mother-in-law. I believe that when Heavenly Father has something for us, no one takes it away from us, but we need to be gritty. Ruth followed her intuition and returned with his mother-in-law to Bethlehem. Although she was new in this place, she was diligent and adaptable to finding work.

I think I can follow her example in my life by remembering that our value is priceless to God, but when we must live in unpleasant situations, each of us reacts in different ways. Ruth took a gritty decision by staying with his mother-in-law and working for better days for both. Despite her pain, Ruth was a determined and persevering woman; who decided to leave her old life behind and go with her mother-in-law. Therefore, she persevered, searching for what Heavenly Father had for her.